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The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices on teachers' job satisfaction, focusing on 224 permanent teachers in the Norala District, Schools Division of South Cotabato. Utilizing a descriptive-evaluative research design and adapted survey questionnaires, the study assesses the extent of HRM practices implementation across key domains such as recruitment, performance management, training, compensation, career planning, and employee welfare. The findings reveal that HRM practices are generally "Very Well Implemented," with high mean scores indicating strong implementation. Teachers report significant job satisfaction, with a grand mean score of 4.45, suggesting that their roles are well-matched to their skills. However, areas such as fringe benefits, and the fairness of performance reviews were noted as needing improvement. A positive correlation (0.534808) between HRM practices and job satisfaction highlights the critical impact of effective HRM. The study aligns with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, showing that motivators like recognition and personal development enhance satisfaction while addressing hygiene factors like compensation can prevent dissatisfaction. The study recommends that schools continuously improve HRM practices, focusing on both motivators and hygiene factors, to further boost job satisfaction and enhance educational outcomes and organizational success.

Keywords: *Human Resource Management, Job Satisfaction*

Introduction

People are the most valuable resource, according to the mission statements found in almost all organizations (Cherif, 2020). Employees are essential to an organization's success. The right personnel will carry out the organization's objective, impact clientele, and accelerate its progress (Peek, 2023). The State is required under the 1987 Constitution to uphold the rights of workers and advance their welfare (DO, 30, s. 2022). The Department of Education is unwavering in its resolve to protect the well-being of all of its employees, including teaching and non-teaching staff members. Reiterating its commitment to protect employee welfare and guarantee organizational efficacy (DepEd, 2018).

Job satisfaction improves work performance and retention by lowering turnover and absenteeism. Human resource (HR) management includes recruiting, training, and motivating people, which is vital to an organization's success because its personnel is its most valuable asset (MVNU Communications, 2023). Effective human resources practices assist organizations in attracting, retaining, and developing talent (Pantoja, 2016), building a mutually beneficial relationship between employers and employees built on shared duties and trust. This is consistent with the "social exchange theory," in which employees supply services in exchange for rewards (Mehwish et al., 2019).

In the field of education, a few factors also contribute to teachers' job satisfaction and happiness. Teachers are more likely to stay in their jobs longer—possibly until retirement—when they are happy with their working conditions. On the other hand, if they are dissatisfied with their work, they might quit to pursue better chances, which would increase the issue of employee turnover (Santiago II, Santos, & Santiago-Centeno, 2022).

The number of teachers in the municipality where the researchers' work has decreased significantly as a result of early resignations or early retirements. Interestingly, some teachers leave their positions in public schools, but their reasons are not extensively documented (Bulawat, 2020). Additionally, previous study does not focus on understanding why these teachers decide to quit. It is also difficult to understand why teachers with experience in public schools want to transfer to other institutions. In light of the aforementioned, the researchers are motivated to assess the human resource management practices and how they affect teachers' job satisfaction, to improve human resource management policies to raise teachers' job satisfaction.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of the implementation of human resource management practices on teachers' job satisfaction. Specifically, the researcher sought to answer the following:

1. What is the extent of human resource management implementation in terms of:
 - 1.1. Recruitment and Selection Practices;
 - 1.2. Performance Management Practices;
 - 1.3. Training and Development practices;
 - 1.4. Compensation Management Practices;
 - 1.5. Career Planning Practices; and

- 1.6. Employee Safety, Health, and Welfare Practices?
2. What is the level of teachers' job satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of human resource management practices and teachers' job satisfaction?

Literature Review

Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management refers to a wide variety of tasks that involve managing people within a business. This includes hiring, training, motivating, evaluating, and rewarding workers (Wilton, 2016). Essentially, human resource management is the process of developing and executing strategies, rules, and practices to manage the relationship between employers and employees. It focuses on how employees are hired and managed in the workplace (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). Human resource management was first introduced in the early 1980s and has since become a critical topic of study. Over the last three decades, HRM has received a lot of attention for its role in improving personnel management and organizational efficiency.

Recent Human Resource Management techniques have arisen in response to new difficulties, and they are increasingly being implemented in a systematic manner rather than as individual components (Laursen and Foss, 2014). Effective human resource management strategies are critical for establishing success and maintaining high performance in the hotel industry (Baum, 2015; Du Plessis, Douangphichit, & Dodd, 2015). The personal interaction between staff and customers in lodging facilities emphasizes the significance of solid Human Resource Management practices in improving employee performance (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). Ashton (2018) sees Human Resource Management practices as critical tools for organizational performance, particularly in the hotel industry (Boella & Goss-Turner, 2013).

Effective human resource management has a direct impact on personnel and, when handled properly, can result in beneficial outcomes. Human Resource Management entails attracting, training, and maintaining skilled employees, ensuring their performance, and keeping them involved with the organization. In contrast, management is concerned with efficiently achieving the organization's goals through its people. Human Resource Management strives to use employees' abilities and knowledge to improve the organization (Dessler, 2015; Yingying, 2017). Human Resource Management essentially handles the human aspect, which encompasses the knowledge, skills, and abilities that contribute to an organization's performance (Hartog et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2015).

Human Resource Management in Recruitment and Selection Practices

The human resource department plays a crucial role in recruitment and selection, which underpin an organization's competitive edge and strategic advantage. An efficient hiring process includes understanding the kind and quantity of workers required, where to look for suitable applicants, and how to draw them in. It also calls for the capacity to assess applicants' work after determining which ones are competent and which ones are not. This methodical approach requires a substantial investment of time and resources, as it involves finding applicants and holding interviews. A transparent hiring policy that addresses job vacancy identification, job analysis, job descriptions, person specifications, and advertising should be a part of any well-run recruitment process (Gamage, 2014).

One of the most important duties of human resource management is recruitment since an organization's human resources have a significant impact on its success or failure (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018). Organizations must maintain or improve their recruiting and selection procedures since hiring is crucial to a business's growth and competitiveness. To accomplish organizational objectives, selection, in particular, entails selecting the top applicants from a pool of individuals who satisfy the job's eligibility standards. (Abu, 2015; Bature, 2019).

Human Resource Management in Performance Management Practices

A company's ability to perform its workforce is essential to its success. Gruman and Saks (2011) state that emphasizing Performance Management Systems (PMS) that increase employee participation is one way to improve performance. Businesses can encourage and control employee involvement and raise job performance levels by managing this participation properly. When implemented properly, performance management is a complex human resource management strategy that enables employers to give feedback to staff members regarding their skills, abilities, and potential development. To define performance goals, evaluate results, and recognize accomplishments, managers collaborate closely with their employees (Kaur & Singla, 2019).

According to Rao (2016), performance management entails doing all essential actions to consistently enhance each employee's performance in line with the short- and long-term objectives of the company. This procedure entails determining and assessing team and individual performance concerning the company's strategic goals (Aguinis, 2019). Furthermore, performance management can be seen as an all-encompassing strategy that considers the culture, communication methods, human resource style, and policies of the company (Armstrong & Baron, 2014).

The organizational environment can influence the performance management method, and as Hart (2018) notes, performance evaluations can have a variety of functions based on the needs of the business, including fostering performance, guaranteeing compliance, or assisting with talent development.

Human Resource Management in Training and Development Practices

Human resources are among the most precious assets an organization may have, hence training and development of these resources is critical. As Eliphas and S (2017), point out, the recognition and encouragement of employees' efforts are critical to an organization's success and effectiveness. To guarantee that employees participate effectively, training programs must be adapted to the needs of both the company and the personnel. When properly planned and managed, these development methods provide employees with new abilities, particularly technical ones, that can improve job performance and keep skills from becoming obsolete (Cobbalah & van der Walt, 2017). Furthermore, policies that promote training and development have a good impact on employee engagement and commitment because they provide possibilities for advancement and indicate the organization's involvement in their professional development (Susomrith et al., 2019; Kozhakhmet et al., 2022a).

In-service training, as defined by Sedega et al. (2018), includes all educational and personal experiences that contribute to an individual's competence and pleasure in their professional role. This type of training is especially important for professionals such as teachers, who gain from increased knowledge and a sharper attitude, inspiring them to work better (Celen et al., 2016). Furthermore, in-service training is critical in improving the professional knowledge, abilities, and competencies of human resources inside a business, resulting in a more capable and motivated workforce (Khan, 2017).

Human Resource Management in Compensation Management Practices

Compensation is an important component of how businesses manage their staff, helping to recruit and retain competent individuals. Most organizations use several strategies to determine how much to pay their employees. The idea is to appropriately compensate employees, which can enhance morale, keep them engaged, and reduce turnover. According to Chiekezie et al. (2017), providing enough compensation encourages employees to remain devoted to their jobs and contributes to the organization's overall performance.

Compensation comprises both financial and non-financial incentives that a firm offers to its employees. According to Sirait (2016), anything a company provides to its employees, whether it is money or benefits, constitutes compensation. When properly managed, remuneration may help employees remain productive and satisfied. Employees who believe they are not being appropriately compensated may depart, making it difficult for the organization to replace them (Shieh, 2018; Petera, 2016). This makes efficient compensation management critical for retaining employees and building a successful workforce.

Human Resource Management in Career Planning Practices

Murali (2023) defines operational human resource management as career development, succession, and career planning. A company that does not provide benefits for career planning and development is likely to see the greatest revenue impact on its goals and programs. Career development programs are used as a retention tactic, particularly in areas where skilled individuals are in high demand. Organizations can reduce competitor allure and improve their ability to retain top talent by giving clear career growth opportunities (Barhate & Dirani, 2022). Keeping skilled individuals is essential for operational efficiency, especially in logistics (Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2020). Implementing effective career development programs within organizations is a complex task riddled with challenges that necessitate careful consideration and strategic planning. Empirical data supports the significant impact of career development on employee engagement and turnover.

Career development efforts have a substantial impact on employee engagement across multiple dimensions in the logistics industry. Career planning stands out among these strategies because it has emerged as a critical component that significantly relates to emotional, cognitive, and behavioral involvement. Career planning comprises providing employees with a clear path for growth inside the firm (Lartey, 2021).

This practice addresses the emotional side of engagement by instilling a sense of purpose and direction. When employees have a strategy for their professional development, they experience less stagnation and discontent, resulting in a better emotional state (Othman & Mahmood, 2019). Additionally, it improves cognitive engagement by fostering a proactive attitude to personal and professional development. Employees who can picture a future within the organization are more likely to engage in cognitive processes such as goal-setting and skill learning (Rumman et al., 2020).

Human Resource Management in Employee Safety, Health, and Welfare Practices

The importance of Human Resource Management (HRM) in determining the success or failure of healthcare system performance was often overestimated. Employee health and safety initiatives should be management's top concern because they not only save lives but also increase productivity and lower costs. These programs should prioritize active employee participation, regular monitoring, and overall well-being (Anthony et al. 2007). Ensuring workplace safety entails developing settings that do not represent a major danger of making people unfit for their occupations.

Workplace health and safety seek to create an atmosphere in which people and organizations may execute their tasks effectively while limiting the risk of injury. This includes developing habits and competencies that promote safe working practices (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2012). Safe working environments have a direct impact on employees' behaviors, which in turn affects productivity. When employees work in a safe setting, they are more likely to sustain high levels of performance while avoiding unnecessary risks.

Job Satisfaction

Employees are critical in carrying out an organization's mission and vision, especially in production. To ensure high quality and quantity of work, employees must adhere to the organization's performance criteria. A suitable work environment is required for employees to achieve their full potential without hurdles (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015).

Job satisfaction is important in encouraging people and inspiring them to produce greater achievements (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015). According to Aggarwal et al. (2023), job satisfaction relates to how driven and content employees are with their jobs. It includes a sense of employment security, professional advancement, and work-life balance, which all contribute to an employee's overall satisfaction when their job matches their expectations. This pleasure not only increases productivity but also helps firms maintain a competitive advantage. It is more than just enjoyment or self-satisfaction; it is about how well an employee's performance and accomplishments match their job objectives.

Riyadi (2019) investigated how job satisfaction, work environment, individual attributes, and salary influence employee performance and stress. The study found that job happiness had a considerable impact on job performance. Employees who are satisfied with their work are more committed to it, do duties more effectively, and care about their own and others' well-being. They also feel safer within the company (Dziuba & Zhuravskaya, 2020). Furthermore, job satisfaction is significant because it influences productivity, motivation, work performance, and overall life satisfaction (Abuhashesh et al., 2019). Employees who are content with their positions are more likely to like their work, perform better, and feel more confident about their future within the firm (Wolniak & Olkiewicz, 2019; Niciejewska, 2017).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-evaluative research design. According to Salaria (2012), descriptive research involves collecting information about current conditions or situations to describe and interpret them. Descriptive-evaluative research design is a study focused on describing both the process and impact of developing and implementing a system (Lau and Kuziemsy, 2016). This research design employs a range of qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis methods. This research approach was used in the study to examine the impact of human resource management practices on teachers' job satisfaction.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the public-school permanent teachers of Norala District. The study used a simple random sampling technique, respondents were determined using Slovin's Formula ($n = N/[1 + Ne^2]$).

Upon getting the sample size, a simple random sampling technique using the draw lots method in selecting the primary subjects of the study was utilized. Using Slovin's formula, the ideal sample size for teachers is two hundred twenty-four (224) out of five hundred thirty-three (533) total population in both secondary and elementary public school permanent teachers.

Instrument

This study used an adapted research questionnaire, the questionnaire was adapted from the study of Tayco (2022) entitled, "Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Outcomes in the Accommodation Facilities in Central Philippines" and O'Riordan (2017) of the Institute of Public Administration entitled, "The Practice of Human Resource Management" and it was modified. It was validated by experts and had undergone a reliability test through pilot testing.

The questionnaire was subdivided into two (2) parts. The first part assessed the influence of human resource management practices in terms of; recruitment and selection practices, performance management practices, training and development practices, compensation management practices, career planning practices, and employee safety, health, and welfare practices, and the second part assessed the teachers' job satisfaction. It was administered to the selected secondary and elementary permanent teachers of Norala District.

Procedure

This study collected data using the described steps. To begin, a letter was addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and administrator of the school covered in the study requesting that the questionnaires be administered. Following approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the participants and collected them as soon as they completed the instrument. Individual questionnaires were utilized to acquire the required data. The responses were transcribed, sorted, and evaluated to yield the results.

Data Analysis

The data gathered about the study was analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Mean was used in determining the extent of implementation of human resource management practices in terms of recruitment and selection, performance management, training and development, compensation management, career planning, employee safety, health

and welfare, and the teacher's job satisfaction.

In interpreting the mean of the responses on the extent of the human resource management practices, the researchers were guided by the scale of interpretation below.

Table 1. *Scale to Interpret the Implementation of Human Resource Management Practices*

Range	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	The HRM Practices Implementation is Very Well Implemented
3.40-4.19	The HRM Practices Implementation is Well Implemented
2.60-3.39	The HRM Practices Implementation is Moderately Implemented
1.80-2.59	The HRM Practices Implementation is Rarely Implemented
1.00-1.79	HRM Practices Implementation is Poorly Implemented

In interpreting the mean of the responses on the teachers' job satisfaction, the researchers were guided by the scale of interpretation below.

Table 2. *Scale to Interpret the Teachers' Job Satisfaction*

Range	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
3.40-4.19	Agree
2.60-3.39	Moderately Agree
1.80-2.59	Disagree
1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Lastly, in determining the significant relationship between the extent of human resource management practices implementation and teachers' job satisfaction, this study utilized Correlation Analysis.

This was interpreted using the table below (Hinkle et. al., 2003).

Table 3. *Strength of Relationship*

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
0.90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00)	Very high positive (negative) correlation
0.70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90)	High positive (negative) correlation
0.50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70)	Moderate positive (negative) correlation
0.30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50)	Low positive (negative) correlation
0.00 to .30 (.00 to -.30)	Negligible correlation

Ethical Considerations

This research project adhered to ethical standards. The respondents willingly participated. Their safety and well-being were prioritized, and no physical, mental, social, or emotional harm occurred. There was always respect for the teachers who participated in this study. The confidentiality of the data collected was ensured.

Results and Discussion

Extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation

Anwar (2024) defines Human Resource Management (HRM) as a holistic process that includes employing the right people, training them, rewarding them fairly, and implementing policies that promote their well-being and productivity. Human resource management (HRM) includes recruitment, employee development, engagement, and retention, all with the goal of keeping people motivated and productive inside the organization.

He emphasizes the importance of human resource management in building strong connections among all organization members, aligning the workforce with the organization's goals and plans, and ensuring that employees' talents and efforts contribute to the organization's overall success.

Recruitment and Selection

As shown in Table 4, human resource management practices in recruitment and selection are rated as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean of 4.73, with the highest-rated indicators being a well-structured interview process and the use of diverse recruitment methods, both with a mean of 4.78, highlighting the organization's strong hiring practices.

However, the lowest-rated indicators, each with a mean of 4.60, indicate that there is room for improvement in communicating the selection criteria and the desired candidate profile, highlighting potential areas of improvement. Since effective recruitment and hiring decisions are critical for identifying the best individuals and accomplishing organizational objectives (Gomathy, 2022), addressing these gaps could improve the organization's HRM practices.

Table 4. *The extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Recruitment and Selection*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The recruitment process in the organization is transparent and fair.	4.75	Very Well Implemented
2.	The selection criteria used by the organization are clearly communicated to all candidates.	4.60	Very Well Implemented
3.	The organization places the right person in the right job.	4.77	Very Well Implemented
4.	The interview process in the organization is well-structured and efficient.	4.78	Very Well Implemented
5.	Candidates are given adequate information about the job role and responsibilities during the recruitment process.	4.76	Very Well Implemented
6.	The recruitment and selection process is free from bias and discrimination.	4.75	Very Well Implemented
7.	The organization is clear about the type of people it needs to employ.	4.60	Very Well Implemented
8.	The HR team provides timely feedback to candidates throughout the recruitment process.	4.77	Very Well Implemented
9.	The organization uses a variety of recruitment methods to reach a diverse pool of candidates.	4.78	Very Well Implemented
10.	The selection process accurately identifies candidates who are the best fit for the job.	4.76	Very Well Implemented
	Grand Mean	4.73	Very Well Implemented

Performance Management

Table 5 reveals that human resource management in performance management practices is assessed as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean score of 4.67. Employees cherish opportunities for discussions about performance and development with their leaders since they considerably increase motivation and engagement. However, concerns regarding the fairness and comprehensiveness of the appraisal process, as indicated in lower ratings, indicate areas for development. According to Maake (2024), effective human resource management and fair performance management systems are critical for optimizing employee performance, and addressing these concerns could improve overall organizational success.

Table 5. *The extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Performance Management*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	Performance goals and expectations are clearly communicated to all employees.	4.62	Very Well Implemented
2.	Regular performance feedback is provided to employees throughout the year.	4.69	Very Well Implemented
3.	The performance appraisal process is fair and unbiased.	4.49	Very Well Implemented
4.	Employees have opportunities to discuss their performance and development with their managers.	4.79	Very Well Implemented
5.	Performance management practices help to identify and reward high performers.	4.75	Very Well Implemented
6.	The performance management system is aligned with the organization's strategic goals.	4.62	Very Well Implemented
7.	Employees receive adequate training and resources to meet performance expectations.	4.69	Very Well Implemented
8.	The performance management process includes a review of both short-term and long-term goals.	4.49	Very Well Implemented
9.	Employees feel motivated and engaged as a result of the performance management practices.	4.79	Very Well Implemented
10.	The performance management process effectively addresses and resolves performance issues and resources to meet performance expectations.	4.75	Very Well Implemented
	Grand Mean	4.67	Very Well Implemented

Training and Development

Table 6. *The extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Training and Development*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The organization provides sufficient training opportunities for employees to develop their skills.	4.63	Very Well Implemented
2.	Training programs are relevant to employees' job roles and responsibilities.	4.45	Very Well Implemented
3.	Employees have access to a variety of development resources, such as workshops and online courses.	4.55	Very Well Implemented
4.	The organization is committed to the ongoing training and development of its employees.	4.85	Very Well Implemented
5.	Training and development programs are regularly updated to meet the changing needs of the organization.	4.29	Very Well Implemented
6.	The organization has an e-learning/e-training program that enhances the knowledge, skills, and abilities of the employees.	4.64	Very Well Implemented

7.	The organization's training and development practices contribute to employee career advancement.	4.45	Very Well Implemented
8.	Training sessions are conducted by knowledgeable and experienced trainers.	4.47	Very Well Implemented
9.	The organization allocates adequate budget and resources for employee training and development.	4.76	Very Well Implemented
10.	Employees can easily provide feedback on the effectiveness of training and development programs.	4.29	Very Well Implemented
Grand Mean		4.54	Very Well Implemented

Table 6 shows that human resource management in training and development is determined as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean score of 4.54. The highest-rated indicator demonstrates employees' significant appreciation for the organization's commitment to continuous training, while the lowest-rated indicators raise worries about the adaptability and feedback mechanisms of these programs. Arulsamy et al. (2023) back up these findings by emphasizing the importance of effective training and development in improving employee performance, job satisfaction, and organizational success. Improving program flexibility and feedback mechanisms is critical for meeting changing needs and enhancing employee performance.

Compensation Management

Table 7 reveals that human resource management practices in compensation management are regarded as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean score of 4.54. The highest-rated measures, both with a mean of 4.79, show that employees are well-informed on compensation criteria and policies, implying that open communication increases employee trust and understanding. However, the lowest-rated factors (mean of 4.34) raise concerns regarding the frequency of compensation evaluations and their impact on employee satisfaction and motivation. According to Daniel (2019), effective and consistent remuneration methods are essential for enhancing corporate engagement and employee happiness, emphasizing the need to address these inequalities.

Table 7. *The extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Compensation Management*

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The organization's compensation practices are fair and transparent.	4.66	Very Well Implemented
2.	The organization's compensation and benefits are competitive compared to other organizations.	4.40	Very Well Implemented
3.	Compensation is aligned with employee performance and contributions.	4.50	Very Well Implemented
4.	Employees are aware of the criteria used to determine their compensation.	4.79	Very Well Implemented
5.	The organization regularly reviews and adjusts compensation to reflect market changes.	4.34	Very Well Implemented
6.	Benefits and perks offered by the organization are valuable and meet employee needs.	4.66	Very Well Implemented
7.	The compensation structure is designed to attract and retain top talent.	4.40	Very Well Implemented
8.	Employees have opportunities to earn bonuses and incentives based on their performance.	4.50	Very Well Implemented
9.	The organization provides clear communication about compensation policies and changes.	4.79	Very Well Implemented
10.	Compensation management practices contribute to employee satisfaction and motivation.	4.34	Very Well Implemented
Grand Mean		4.54	Very Well Implemented

Career Planning

Table 8 shows that human resource management practices in career planning are assessed as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean score of 4.42. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 4.76, indicates that employees understand the rationale for their salary, demonstrating successful communication and respected transparency. However, the lowest-rated indic, with a mean of 3.92, implies that employees may not perceive the benefits and perks to be valuable or matched with their needs, indicating a need for development in this area. Ariyanto et al. (2020) support this by highlighting that good career planning and employee training have a favorable impact on career growth, even if career management practices alone do not mitigate this benefit. This emphasizes the necessity of open communication regarding compensation and aligning benefits with employee expectations to improve career growth and happiness.

Table 8. *The extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Career Planning*

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The organization's compensation practices are fair and transparent.	4.63	Very Well Implemented
2.	The organization's compensation and benefits are competitive compared to other organizations.	4.50	Very Well Implemented
3.	Compensation is aligned with employee performance and contributions.	4.45	Very Well Implemented
4.	Employees are aware of the criteria used to determine their compensation.	4.76	Very Well Implemented
5.	The organization regularly reviews and adjusts compensation to reflect market changes.	4.29	Very Well Implemented
6.	Benefits and perks offered by the organization are valuable and meet	4.01	Well Implemented

7.	employee needs. The compensation structure is designed to attract and retain top talent.	4.16	Well Implemented
8.	Employees have opportunities to earn bonuses and incentives based on their performance.	4.33	Very Well Implemented
9.	The organization provides clear communication about compensation policies and changes.	4.38	Very Well Implemented
10.	Compensation management practices contribute to employee satisfaction and motivation.	4.69	Very Well Implemented
Grand Mean		4.42	Very Well Implemented

Employee Safety, Health and Welfare

Table 9 indicates that human resource management practices in employee safety, health, and welfare are rated as "Very Well Implemented" with a mean score of 4.42. Employees value the organization's support of work-life balance, with a mean rating of 4.79. However, the accessibility of wellness programs and health services was rated lower (3.92), indicating an opportunity for improvement. Melhem et al. (2024) argues that including occupational health and safety (OHS) within HRM frameworks improves employee well-being and organizational resilience. While the organization's work-life balance efforts are helpful, it is advised that wellness programs be made more accessible and effective to further promote overall employee health.

Table 9. *Extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation in Employee Safety, Health, and Welfare*

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1.	The organization has effective policies in place to ensure employee safety at work.	4.66	Very Well Implemented
2.	Employees receive regular training on health and safety procedures.	4.40	Very Well Implemented
3.	The workplace is equipped with the necessary safety equipment and resources.	4.50	Very Well Implemented
4.	The organization promotes a healthy work-life balance for employees.	4.79	Very Well Implemented
5.	There are clear procedures for reporting and addressing safety hazards.	4.34	Very Well Implemented
6.	The organization provides access to wellness programs and health resources.	3.92	Well Implemented
7.	Employee health and safety concerns are promptly addressed by management.	4.18	Well Implemented
8.	The organization regularly reviews and updates its safety and health policies.	4.28	Very Well Implemented
9.	Employees are encouraged to participate in health and safety initiatives.	4.48	Very Well Implemented
10.	The organization supports mental health and provides resources for managing stress.	4.61	Very Well Implemented
Grand Mean		4.42	Very Well Implemented

Summary of the Extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation

The result reveals that generally, the extent of implementation of human resource management practices in both elementary and secondary schools in Norala District is "Very Well Implemented" with a mean of 4.58.

Table 10. *Summary of the Extent of Human Resource Management Practices Implementation*

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1.	Recruitment and Selection	4.73	Very Well Implemented
2.	Performance Management	4.67	Very Well Implemented
3.	Training and Development	4.54	Very Well Implemented
4.	Compensation Management	4.54	Very Well Implemented
5.	Career Planning	4.42	Very Well Implemented
6.	Employee Safety, Health and Welfare	4.42	Very Well Implemented
Grand Mean		4.55	Very Well Implemented

Teachers Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to employees' level of contentment with their jobs, which includes not only their daily responsibilities but also their relationships with colleagues and superiors, their satisfaction with organizational policies, and the impact of their work on their personal lives (BasuMallick, 2021). High job satisfaction increases productivity, stimulates people, improves work performance, and leads to general well-being (Abuhashesh et al., 2019).

Table 11 reveals that teachers are "Very Satisfied" on their job with a mean score of 4.46. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 4.87, indicates that teachers feel that their jobs are rewarding and well-suited to their abilities. This shows that aligning job tasks with teacher's competencies is highly regarded. However, the lowest-rated measure, with a mean of 3.84, indicates that teachers

believe the fringe benefits provided are inadequate, indicating a possible gap that may impair overall job satisfaction. Rokeman et al. (2023) support these findings, stating that job satisfaction has a major impact on teachers' dedication, productivity, and retention.

Table 11. *Level of Teachers' Job Satisfaction*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	Teachers are satisfied with their current salary and compensation.	4.56	Very Satisfied
2.	Opportunities for career advancement and promotion are adequate for teachers.	4.71	Very Satisfied
3.	Supervision provided by school administrators is supportive and effective.	4.15	Satisfied
4.	Fringe benefits offered by the organization meet the needs of teachers.	3.84	Satisfied
5.	Operating conditions within the school environment are conducive to effective teaching.	4.77	Very Satisfied
6.	Teachers have positive and collaborative relationships with their co-workers.	4.80	Very Satisfied
7.	The nature of the work assigned to teachers is fulfilling and aligns with their skills.	4.87	Very Satisfied
8.	Communication between teachers and school administration is clear and efficient.	4.36	Very Satisfied
9.	Teachers feel that their contributions are valued and recognized by the school.	4.32	Very Satisfied
10.	The school provides adequate resources and support to help teachers perform their duties effectively.	4.16	Satisfied
	Grand Mean	4.45	Very Satisfied

Relationship on the Extent of Human Resource Management Practices and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Table 12 shows that there is a moderate positive relationship (0.534808) between human resource management (HRM) practices and teacher's job satisfaction. This suggests that successful HRM practices improve teacher job satisfaction, as evidenced by a p-value of 1.57E-10, which is less than 0.05. This finding is consistent with Alkhamis's (2024) conclusion that HRM strategies have a considerable impact on employee job satisfaction and are favorably associated with employee outcomes when applied properly. Although HRM methods have a direct impact on job satisfaction, their impact on employee commitment and turnover intention is mediated by HRM effectiveness. Thus, improving HRM strategies such as succession planning, talent development, and performance management could increase job satisfaction.

Table 12. *Relationship on the Extent of Human Resource Management Practices and Teachers' Job Satisfaction*

	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Extent of Human Resource Management Practices x Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.534808	1.57E-10	significant

Note: $p < .05$ to signify the significant relationship

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study effectively examined the impact of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices on teachers' job satisfaction. The analysis reveals that HRM practices across various domains—such as recruitment and selection, performance management, training and development, compensation management, career planning, and employee safety, health, and welfare—are generally rated as "Very Well Implemented," with mean scores reflecting strong implementation (Table 10). Teachers, in turn, report high levels of job satisfaction, with a grand mean score of 4.45, indicating that their roles are meaningful and well-suited to their skills. However, the study does identify opportunities for improvement, particularly in fringe benefits and the impartiality of performance reviews (Table 11).

The substantial positive correlation of 0.534808 between HRM practices and teachers' job satisfaction (Table 12) supports the conclusion that effective HRM practices have a considerable impact on job satisfaction, consistent with Alkhamis' findings (2024). This highlights the significance of continuously improving HRM practices to increase job satisfaction even more.

This study's findings are consistent with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which states that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are impacted by two distinct elements: motivators and hygiene issues. Motivators such as recognition, achievement, and personal development are linked to good performance management, career planning, and training, and they have a direct impact on job satisfaction. Hygiene issues, such as remuneration and workplace policies, might help prevent unhappiness when addressed properly, but they do not always boost satisfaction.

This study found a substantial positive link between HRM practices and teacher job satisfaction, which validates Herzberg's theory. Improving HRM practices, particularly those that function as motivators, can lead to higher overall job satisfaction. Furthermore, addressing gaps in fringe benefits and the fairness of performance appraisals—key hygiene factors—can help to reduce unhappiness and build a more cheerful workplace. Schools can increase job satisfaction by continuously refining HRM processes, thereby boosting

educational outcomes and adding to the organization's success.

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that schools should prioritize continuous enhancement of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices to increase teachers' job satisfaction. Efforts should be focused on areas recognized as needing improvement, such as fringe benefits and the fairness of performance reviews. Addressing these gaps, which are essential hygiene aspects according to Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, may mitigate dissatisfaction and build a happier work environment. Furthermore, schools should prioritize motivators such as recognition, achievement, and opportunity for personal development through effective performance management, career planning, and training activities. By refining these HRM practices, schools can improve job satisfaction, educational outcomes, and overall organizational effectiveness.

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